

Optimization of production well operations in the water distribution system using an algorithm

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The non-linear programming approach has been highly adopted for multi-reservoir and multi-source water distribution systems. A perfect model can be easily developed for obtaining least cost pump operation policy for a multi-source, multi-tank water distribution system. The algorithm has the advantage of being computationally efficient while incorporating the non-linear characteristic of the water distribution network. In addition, the algorithm has the advantage of providing several feasible solutions to the control problem, which then provides the system operator with increased flexibility. Simulated annealing is a combinatorial optimization method that uses the metropolis algorithm to evaluate the acceptability of alternate arrangements and slowly converge to an optimum solution. Metropolis algorithm was developed to provide the simulation of a system of atoms at a high temperature that slowly cools to its ground energy state.

The author developed a management model to link the Chandler water distribution model (EPANET. It's a computer program that performs extended simulation of hydraulic and water quality) with the Chandler groundwater flow model (MODFLOW. It's also a computer program that numerically solves three-dimensional groundwater flow equation using a finite difference method) under an optimization framework (Genetic Algorithm). EPANET AND MODFLOW are used for simulation and modeling purposes. Their purpose basically is to optimize the well pump operation such pump energy cost is minimized. Genetic Algorithm was used to solve the optimization problem (function) with objectives like energy, drawdown. The author describes Genetic Algorithm for single objective and multi-objective optimization problems taking into account the genetic operators for these optimization problems.

This study developed a conjunctive management model that has the capability of providing the 24-hour real time well pump operations while forecasting the groundwater system and water distribution system responses for 7 days. The management objectives are energy cost minimization, daily tank level deviation minimization, weekly drawdown minimization, tank water residence time minimization, system reliability maximization, pressure violation minimization. The multi objective model is a binary integer nonlinear programming problem (BINLP), which involves groundwater modeling and hydraulic pipe network modeling. Before conducting the optimization, the groundwater and water distribution models were run using the documented well pump operations during a week as the original model to develop the baseline against the optimized model and two extreme

cases. From the cases analysis, the author was able to acknowledge the upper and lower limits for all objective function values.

Genetic Algorithm solver was used in the study for solving the BINLP due to the intrinsic binary chromosome in GA. GA, one of the evolutionary algorithms, has a potential to search for global or near global optimal solution while only analyzing a small fraction of possible solutions. GA is a derivative free algorithm and only requires the objective function evaluation. GA evolves the solutions from multiple starting points and uses probabilistic transition rules to reduce the possibility of being trapped in a local optimum. In past decade, GA has become one of important optimization techniques to solve the water resources system optimization problem. Parallel Genetic Algorithm was used to determine the optimized weight and penalties for the function. Parallelization of the current genetic algorithm solver and the use of a cluster of computers have to be implemented to obtain the solution much less than 24 hours computation time. The GA links EPANET and MODFLOW as a simulation optimization model to obtain the optimal 23 well pump daily operation patterns.

The linkage between the Chandler EPANET and MODFLOW models was made through the 23 well pumps. The author assumed that the groundwater head changes were insignificant within a day. Therefore, the groundwater levels in EPANET were updated weekly using MODFLOW results. The weekly stress period was considered in the groundwater model. The MODFLOW well package was updated using the EPANET pumping rates. He pointed out seven steps in transferring data between the EPANET and MODFLOW for the transient simulation.

A user interface for the chandler production well management model was developed in Microsoft Excel. The calculations within the codes and the results produced in between and finally are transported into the excel sheet for further processing, so as to make them presentable and distinguishable. The energy cost and pressures violation were found to be the most sensitive to the system because these two objectives give vary large numbers. The energy cost minimization and pressure violation minimization considered were the first priorities. In order to generate a 24 hour real time well pump operations, the management objectives should be follow;

Objective 1: Energy cost minimization.

The energy (kW-h) consumed by a well pump i at time t is calculated by

$$E_{i,t} = \frac{\gamma_w Q'_{i,t} H_{i,t}}{\eta_{i,t}}$$

Where w is the water specific weight; $H_{i,t}$ is the lifted head by the pump i at time t ; and $\eta_{i,t}$ is the pump efficiency for pump i at time t .

Objective 2: Daily Tank Level Deviation Minimization

The tank level deviation minimization objective function is

$$\min \quad \Sigma \Sigma [H_{K,24n}^{Tank} - H_{k,24(n-1)}^{Tank}]^2$$

$$z_{i,t} \in (0,1) \quad k \quad n$$

Where $H_{K,24n}^{Tank}$ is the tank level at tank k at the end of day n ; and $H_{K,24n}^{Tank}$ is the tank level at the beginning of day n .

Objective 3: Weekly Drawdown Minimization

Only positive drawdowns are considered in the objective function.

$$\min \quad \sum \max [0, \phi_{i,T} - \phi_{i,0}]$$

$$z_{i,t} \in (0,1) \quad i$$

Where $\phi_{i,T}$ is the groundwater head at pumping site i , last time step T ; and $\phi_{i,0}$ is the

Initial groundwater head at pumping site i .

Objective 4: Tank Water Residence Time Minimization

The tank water residence time (TR) is defined as the duration of water residing in the tank. The objective for the total tank water residence time minimization is;

$$\min \quad \sum \sum \left[1, \frac{S_{i,t}}{b_{i,t}} \right]$$

$$z_{i,t} \in (0,1) \quad i \quad t$$

Objective 5: System Reliability Maximization

The objective function is

$$\min \quad \frac{1}{N_T \times T} \sum \sum \text{INT}[TR_{i,t}]$$

$$z_{i,t} \in (0,1) \quad i \quad t$$

Where $TR_{i,t}$ is the residence time at a time t .

The study identified the presence of conflicting objectives. With increasing energy consumption the pressure violations decreased due to which residence time increased and so the reliability increased. Thus, the author was able to set up a compromising solution so that it would be able to tackle all the conflicts without introducing any potential problem in the water distribution system.

The total daily tank level deviation was found to have increase in case 1 (optimized results, table 5.2) due to not keeping tank full or empty as in the original model and extreme cases. Most of the tanks followed a daily periodic pattern, which avoids developments of high pressures at nodes in the vicinity of the tanks. However, some tanks are not periodic due to non-periodic booster bump operations to the tanks.

Decrease in the energy values in case 2 and case 3 (optimized results for case 2 and 3) are higher than the case 1 values by 50. The pumping rates also increase in case 2 and case 3. Also due to increase pumping rate the tank water levels have been increased. The total daily tank level deviation has decreased for cases 2 and 3. Higher pumping rates resulted in an increase in the system reliability in cases 2 and 3. Also, total drawdowns have increase in comparison to case 1, most of the drawdown occurs at the northeastern part of the city.

Genetic algorithm has proved to be effective for the operational optimization problem. It is fast and efficient compared to other non-linear solvers. Satisfactory and consistent results were produced after optimization. Optimizing a water distribution system using GA under a parallel processing environment creates a vast set of solutions and the study of their interrelationship. Parallel processing helped to recognize the best weighting coefficients for the optimization equation.

The author recommended that original operation pattern can be improved to avoid high water levels in the tanks and reduce the unnecessary high system reliability. The drawdown maximization can be investigated in the future study for withdrawing more groundwater from the aquifer without compromising the environment detriment. The Chandler production well management model can be expanded to consider conjunctive use of the surface water and groundwater.

Literature

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